

United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE
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U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service
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Sacramento, CA 95814

In Reply Refer To:
08FBDT00-2018-F-0238

April 22, 2020

Frances Malamud-Roam
San Francisco District, U.S. Army Corps of Engineers
Regulatory Division
450 Golden Gate Avenue, 4th Floor
San Francisco, CA 94102

Subject: Formal Section 7 Consultation on the Union Sanitary District Emergency Outfall Project (U.S. Army Corps of Engineers File No. 2017-00414S)

Dear Ms. Malamud-Roam:

This letter is in response to the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers' (Corps) May 28, 2018, request for consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) on the potential effects of the proposed Union Sanitary District (District) Emergency Outfall Project in the City of Union City, Alameda County, California. Your request was received by the Service on June 4, 2018. The Corps determined that the project may adversely affect the federally endangered salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*) but is not likely to adversely affect the endangered California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*). Regarding taxonomic assignment and nomenclature for the California clapper rail, until a time when the Service officially adopts changes made by the American Ornithologists' Union (from California clapper rail [*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*] to Ridgway's Rail [*Rallus obsoletus*]), the Service maintains the use of California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*) as used in this current correspondence. This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*) (Act), and in accordance with the implementing regulations pertaining to interagency cooperation (50 CFR 402).

In reviewing this project, the Service has relied upon: (1) the Corps' May 28, 2018, letter requesting consultation with the enclosed *Biological Resources Assessment for Union Sanitary District Emergency Outfall Project* prepared by WRA, Inc. (consultant) dated March 2018; (2) emails between the Corps, Service and consultant; and (3) other information available to the Service.

The Service does not concur with the Corps' determination that the proposed project is not likely to adversely affect the California clapper rail due to potential effects to individuals and habitat.

Therefore, the remainder of this document is the Service's biological opinion on the effects of the proposed project on the California Clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse.

Consultation History

June 4, 2018	The Service received a request from the Corps for informal consultation on the Union Sanitary District Emergency Outfall Project.
June 3, 2019	The Service sent an email requesting additional information from the Corps regarding the project description and species effects.
June 14, 2019	The Service received additional information about this project in an email from the Corps.
July 8, 2019	The Service sent an email to the Corps asking clarifying questions.
July 19, 2019	The consultant sent an email to the Service and the Corps responding to the Service's June 8, 2019 email.
August 21, 2019	The consultant drafted the 2019 California clapper rail survey results report.
October 11, 2019	Brown and Caldwell drafted information regarding what construction equipment will be utilized.

BIOLOGICAL OPINION

Description of the Proposed Action

The Service has summarized its understanding of the project from the various documents and emails provided during consultation. The purpose of the proposed project is to make improvements to an emergency outfall to reduce the maintenance activities associated with the emergency outfall flap gate and increase the reliability of the Emergency Outfall operation during wet weather events. Under current conditions, the emergency outfall flap gate is submerged below water during high tides and is exposed during low tides. This presents a maintenance issue as the water brings in sediments that bury the flap gate and promotes vegetation growth, which impedes the operation of the flap gate. The District currently performs a maintenance program to clear the sediment and vegetation growth once every three months.

The District proposes to raise the emergency outfall pipe and flap gate above high tide to avoid future maintenance issues. The District will replace a portion of the existing pipe located under the access road and within a portion of Old Alameda Creek. A new outfall structure will also be installed with bank stabilization. Stabilizing the creek banks around the new outfall will require the installation of rip rap both above and below the high tide line.

The following activities would be included as elements of this project:

- Abandonment of approximately 40 linear feet of 48-inch diameter pipeline by filling with approximately 20 cubic yards of flowable fill.
- Replacement of approximately 25 linear feet of 48-inch diameter pipeline by open cut, requiring excavation and backfill of approximately 250 cubic yards of soil.
- Construction of approximately 100 linear feet of 48-inch diameter redundant pipeline by open cut. This will require excavation and backfill of approximately 1,000 cubic yards of soil.
- Construction of a concrete outlet structure consisting of a slab, headwalls, and wing walls. Total concrete volume of the structure will be approximately 50 cubic yards. There will be approximately 18 inches of aggregate base below the concrete structure.
- Placement of up to approximately 112 cubic yards of stone rip rap for bank and channel protection at the end of the concrete outlet structure. This will involve the removal of approximately 250 cubic yards of accumulated sediment to facilitate placement of the rip rap on the more solid channel bank that has been covered by sediment.
- Installation of approximately 160 linear feet of temporary sheet pile cofferdam. Residual seepage within the cofferdam will be collected and filtered prior to discharge.
- Construction of up to approximately 40 feet of 12-inch diameter pipeline on the adjacent wastewater treatment plant site. This will require excavation and backfill of approximately 40 cubic yards of soil.
- Construction of an access riser on the existing outfall pipeline on the adjacent wastewater treatment plant site. This will require excavation and backfill of approximately 10 cubic yards of soil.

Construction will include: (1) clearing and grubbing the site; (2) sheet pile cofferdam installation; (3) construction of rip rap apron; (4) pipeline construction; and (5) outlet structure construction. Anticipated activity descriptions and expected equipment are briefly described below.

Clearing and grubbing (work on bank) will consist of removing vegetation using hand-held power tools. Possible equipment could include 2 string-line trimmers operated simultaneously for 8 hours a day for 1 day.

The sheet pile cofferdam (in-water work) is anticipated to be constructed using a vibratory head on an excavator or crane. Possible equipment could include: (1) a Caterpillar 330 excavator or

mobile crane such as a Link-Belt HC-238B and (2) a Caterpillar 926M wheel loader. This equipment is anticipated to operate simultaneously for 8 hours a day for 1 week.

The rip rap apron construction will include removal of existing sediment using an excavator and placement of rip rap using an excavator. Sediment will be removed, and rip rap delivered, by dump truck and moved using a wheeled loader. Possible equipment could include the following: (1) a Caterpillar 330 excavator; (2) a Caterpillar 926M wheel loader; (3) a 14-yard dump truck; and (4) a diesel generator. This equipment is anticipated to operate simultaneously for 8 hours a day for 1 week.

The pipeline construction will include excavation, pipeline placement, and backfilling using an excavator. Pipe installation will be assisted by a wheeled loader and materials will be delivered by dump truck and concrete trucks. Possible equipment could include the following: (1) a Caterpillar 330 excavator; (2) a Caterpillar 926M wheel loader; (3) a 14-yard dump truck; (4) a concrete truck; and (5) a diesel generator. This equipment is anticipated to operate simultaneously for 8 hours a day for 1 week although concrete trucks and dump trucks are not likely to operate at the same time.

The outlet construction will include excavation, subgrade construction, forming and pouring the concrete structure, and backfilling the structure. An excavator will be used to excavate and material will be transported by a dump truck. Subgrade construction and pouring the structure will include the use of concrete trucks. Backfill of the structure will include use of an excavator and plate compactors assisted by a wheeled loader. Possible equipment could include the following: (1) a Caterpillar 330 excavator; (2) a Caterpillar 926M wheel loader; (3) a 14-yard dump truck; (4) a concrete truck; (5) a plate compactor; and (6) a diesel generator.

Not all equipment listed above is anticipated to be operated at the same time. It is likely that the following equipment will be operated simultaneously: (1) the Caterpillar 330 excavator, Caterpillar 926M wheel loader, and 14-yard dump truck or (2) the Caterpillar 330 excavator, plate compactor, and diesel generator. These will be operated for 8 hours a day for 2 weeks.

There will be use of other pieces of equipment such as hand-held power tools, personnel vehicles, etc. A full list was not provided to the Service.

Conservation Measures

1. Prior to the initiation of construction, the biological monitor shall provide an endangered species training program to all personnel involved in project construction. At a minimum, the employee education program shall consist of a brief presentation by persons knowledgeable about the biology and legislative protection of protected species with potential to occur in or adjacent to the Action Area, to explain concerns to contractors, their employees, and agency personnel involved with implementation of the project. The program shall include the following: a description of such species and their habitat needs, any reports of occurrences in the Action Area, an explanation of the status of these species and their protection under state and federal legislation, and a list of

measures being taken to reduce impacts to protected species during the work. Fact sheets containing this information shall be provided to the project foreman.

2. Prior to ground disturbance, all ruderal non-native grassland and coastal brackish marsh shall be carefully removed from the impact footprint under the supervision of a qualified biologist. The biologist will first conduct a thorough nest search within vegetation to be removed. If active small mammal nests with potential to be salt marsh harvest mouse nests are observed, a 50-foot buffer will be established around the nest until the biologist has determined that the young are independent of the nest. Vegetation will then be removed using only hand tools or hand-operated power tools to carefully remove vegetation down to bare ground.
3. To prevent wildlife entrapment, equipment and materials shall be staged in developed areas within the District's wastewater treatment plant; they shall not be staged adjacent to Old Alameda Creek where they could provide cover for small mammals that normally reside in the adjacent vegetation. Alternatively, exclusion fencing may be installed along the top of bank of Old Alameda Creek for 200 feet in either direction from the center of the Action Area, and the fencing shall be inspected weekly by the qualified biologist. Exclusion fencing may double as erosion control.
4. A qualified biologist will be present for initial ground disturbance within the banks of Old Alameda Creek. Following initial ground disturbance, the biologist will monitor on an as-needed basis for any new groundbreaking within the banks of the creek.
5. If excavations or trenches are not backfilled on the same day as excavation, they shall either be covered so as to prevent small mammals from falling in, or they shall be provided with exit ramps suitable for small mammals to escape on their own.
6. Work hours shall be limited to half an hour after sunrise to half an hour prior to sunset. Night work shall be avoided to the maximum extent feasible.
7. If any mouse or shrew is observed at any time during construction, work shall not be initiated or shall be stopped immediately until the animal leaves the vicinity of the work area of its own volition. The project biologist shall direct the contractor on how to proceed accordingly. Neither the biologist nor any other persons at the site shall pursue, capture, handle, or harass any potential protected species observed.
8. Construction work shall be limited to the period between September 1 and January 31 to avoid the California clapper rail nesting season.
9. Best management practices shall be used to lessen potential impacts to sensitive habitats. These include the use of silt fencing, wattles, and other appropriate stormwater pollution prevention measures. For in-water work, a coffer dam or similar shall be installed at low tide with oversight from a qualified biologist to prevent or minimize increases in turbidity during work in open water.

10. The temporary impacts will be compensated for by on-site revegetation. The ruderal non-native grassland habitat will be allowed to revegetate naturally and is expected to have cover similar to pre-disturbance conditions within 1-2 years after completion of construction. The marsh habitat will be revegetated using plants salvaged on-site and/or with plants purchased at a local nursery. The revegetation area will be monitored annually until cover is similar to that of the adjacent undisturbed areas. It is expected to take 3-5 years for the marsh vegetation to return to pre-disturbance cover amounts.

Action Area

The Action Area is defined in 50 CFR § 402.02, as “all areas to be affected directly or indirectly by the Federal action and not merely the immediate area involved in the action.” The Action Area for this consultation encompasses all areas that may be directly or indirectly affected as a result of activities for the project and the broader area that, while outside the project footprint, may be directly or indirectly affected by vibrations, noise, or movement associated with the proposed project.

The emergency outfall to Old Alameda Creek is located on a 1-acre parcel at the end of an access road off Veasy Street, in the City of Union City, Alameda, County, California. The total Action Area is approximately 6.2 acres and consists of: (1) the 1.2 acres of the physical project area (areas of ground disturbance and access/staging areas) and (2) approximately 5 acres of salt marsh habitat within 656 feet (200 meters) of construction activities where California clapper rails may be affected from visual and noise disturbance. This includes the marsh on the other side of Old Alameda Creek from the project up to the levee.

Analytical Framework for the Jeopardy Determination

Section 7(a)(2) of the Act requires that Federal agencies ensure that any action they authorize, fund, or carry out is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species. “Jeopardize the continued existence of” means to engage in an action that reasonably will be expected, directly or indirectly, to reduce appreciably the likelihood of both the survival and recovery of a listed species in the wild by reducing the reproduction, numbers, or distribution of that species (50 CFR § 402.02).

The jeopardy analysis in this biological opinion considers the effects of the proposed Federal action, and any cumulative effects, on the rangewide survival and recovery of the listed species. It relies on four components: (1) the *Status of the Species*, which describes the current rangewide condition of the species, the factors responsible for that condition, and its survival and recovery needs; (2) the *Environmental Baseline*, which analyzes the current condition of the species in the Action Area without the consequences to the listed species caused by the proposed action, the factors responsible for that condition, and the relationship of the Action Area to the survival and recovery of the species; (3) the *Effects of the Action*, which includes all effects that are caused by the proposed Federal action; and (4) the *Cumulative Effects*, which evaluates the effects of future, non-Federal activities in the Action Area on the species. The *Effects of the Action* and *Cumulative Effects* are added to the *Environmental Baseline* and in light of the *Status of the Species*, the Service formulates its opinion as to whether the proposed action is likely to

jeopardize the continued existence of listed species.

Status of the Species

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

There are two subspecies of the salt marsh harvest mouse: the northern subspecies (*R. r. halicoetes*) and the southern subspecies (*R. r. raviventris*) both of which are listed as endangered. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' range-wide status, please refer to the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California*, available at: https://www.fws.gov/sfbaydelta/EndangeredSpecies/RecoveryPlanning/Tidal_Marsh/Documents/TMRP_Volume1_RP.pdf (Service 2013). Critical habitat has not been designated for this species. Threats evaluated during the drafting of the recovery plan and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species since its publication, with loss of habitat being the most significant effect. While there have been continued losses of salt marsh harvest mouse habitat throughout the various recovery units, including the Central/Southern San Francisco Bay Recovery Unit where the proposed project is located, to date no project has proposed a level of effects for which the Service has issued a biological opinion determining jeopardy for the species. The Service is in the process of developing our current 5-year review for the species.

California Clapper Rail

The status of California clapper rail and information about its biology, ecology, distribution, and current threats is available in the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California*, available at: https://www.fws.gov/sfbaydelta/EndangeredSpecies/RecoveryPlanning/Tidal_Marsh/Documents/TMRP_Volume1_RP.pdf (Service 2013). Critical habitat has not been designated for this species. Threats evaluated during the drafting of the recovery plan and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species since its publication, with loss of habitat being the most significant effect. While there have been continued losses of California clapper rail habitat throughout the various recovery units, including the Central/Southern San Francisco Bay Recovery Unit where the proposed project is located, to date no project has proposed a level of effects for which the Service has issued a biological opinion determining jeopardy for the species. The Service is in the process of developing our current 5-year review for the species.

Environmental Baseline

Environmental Baseline refers to the condition of the listed species or its designated critical habitat in the Action Area, without the consequences to the listed species or designated critical habitat caused by the proposed action. The Environmental Baseline includes the past and present impacts of all Federal, State, or private actions and other human activities in the Action Area, the anticipated impacts of all proposed Federal projects in the Action Area that have already undergone formal or early section 7 consultation, and the impact of State or private actions which are contemporaneous with the consultation in process. The consequences to listed species

or designated critical habitat from ongoing agency activities or existing agency facilities that are not within the agency's discretion to modify are part of the *Environmental Baseline*.

The proposed project is located on the eastern bank of Old Alameda Creek, partially within the western city limits of Union City. The project site is located partially on District property and developed lands of the District wastewater treatment plant borders the site to the east. The surrounding landscape is dominated by the Eden Landing Ecological Reserve, which includes restored salt ponds, adjacent diked marshes, upland transitional areas, and Old Alameda Creek, a channelized Alameda Flood Control District flood control channel that experiences tidal fluctuations and is bound by levees on either side.

The project site is dominated by a developed access road, which is located between the southeastern bank of Old Alameda Creek and the District treatment plant. The upper elevations of the creek banks along the road support ruderal, non-native herbaceous vegetation that transitions downslope into emergent brackish marsh and open water. The existing outfall structure to be replaced crosses under the existing access road and empties out into open water within the creek. The outfall discharge point is located below the high tide line and is submerged for portions of the day during high tide cycles. To maintain its function of providing an emergency discharge point into the creek, the outfall area requires maintenance several times each year to clear sediment buildup. Immediately west of the outfall line, there is a ramp from the access road to the creek to provide equipment access to the outfall for maintenance. Further west, an Alameda County Flood Control District outfall structure also discharges water into the creek.

The District holds a National Pollutant Discharge Elimination System permit to discharge final effluent to Old Alameda Creek within the Action Area under wet weather conditions. Final effluent is conveyed from the Alvarado Effluent Pump Station at the wastewater treatment plant, under the access road within the Action Area, and out to the south channel of Old Alameda Creek by the 48-inch diameter emergency outfall pipeline. A system of valves and piping located at the wastewater treatment plant control the flow to the creek.

Ruderal Non-native Grassland

This plant community was found in approximately 0.14 acre on the upper banks of Old Alameda Creek and in the southwest corner of the physical project area. Ruderal grassland within the project area is dominated by wild radish (*Raphanus sativus*), slender wild oat (*Avena barbata*), and ripgut brome (*Bromus diandrus*), with cheeseweed mallow (*Malva cf. parviflora*), black mustard (*Brassica nigra*), and other weedy, non-native species.

Developed

Approximately 0.52 acre of developed area are located within the physical project area and include the District wastewater treatment plant infrastructure, Alameda County Flood Control and District outfalls, and access roads. Developed areas also include the area immediately upslope of the District outfall discharge area, where vegetation has been disturbed by outfall maintenance activities.

Several planted landscape trees are located along the boundary between the physical project area access road and the District wastewater treatment plant. All are mature trees, and this community supports little to no ground cover. Tree species include non-native Australian blackwood (*Acacia melanoxylon*) and Monterey pine (*Pinus radiata*).

Coastal Brackish Marsh

Within the physical project area, 0.33 acre of coastal brackish marsh occurs along the lower banks and marsh plane of Old Alameda Creek. The larger Action Area includes an approximate additional 5 acres of coastal brackish marsh minus the open water of Old Alameda Creek. Coastal brackish marsh within the physical project area is located approximately 3 miles upstream from its mouth at South San Francisco Bay, and is tidally influenced. Dominant plant species included cattail (*Typha* spp), common reed (*Phragmites australis*), tall wheat grass (*Elymus* cf. *ponticus*), marsh Jaumea (*Jaumea carnosa*), broadleaved pepperweed, (*Lepidium latifolium*), fat hen (*Atriplex prostrata*), marsh gumplant (*Grindelia stricta*), and pickleweed (*Salicornia virginica*). Vegetation displayed zonation typical of coastal brackish marsh, with a transition from gumplant to pepperweed and marsh jaumea in the intertidal zone, to tall, dense cattail with limited thatch in the semi-permanently to permanently flooded zone. The marsh/upland transition is abrupt due to the change in grade from the channel to the access road/levee.

Open Water

Open water within the physical project area is characterized by unvegetated mudflats that are semi-permanently to permanently flooded with the tidal brackish waters of Old Alameda Creek. Approximately 0.11 acre of open water occurs within the physical project area but is a little larger when including the total Action Area. The District emergency outfall discharges into one of the larger open water areas, and maintenance activities and/or scouring from the outfall appears to maintain the depth and limit the vegetation growth in this area. The other major open water area occurs in the western physical project area at the Alameda County Flood Control District discharge site, and it is likely that either maintenance and/or scouring from discharging water into the creek maintain the depth and limited vegetation growth in this open water area.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

Salt marsh harvest mice been documented to occur at various locations throughout Eden Landing Preserve both north and south of the Action Area (California Department of Fish and Wildlife 2017 as cited in the Biological Resources Assessment; San Francisco Estuary Institute 2009 as cited in the Biological Resources Assessment), and the Action Area is located within the Central/Southern San Francisco Bay Recovery Unit (Service 2013). Brackish marsh along the creek banks provides habitat of suitable species composition, density and height to support this species. Brackish marsh vegetation along the portion of creek bed within the Action Area is dominated by cattails with vertical structure and limited thatch which would provide suitable cover for the mouse, so this provides only marginal quality habitat. The mouse may also occur in ruderal, non-native grasslands within the Action Area for high tide escape cover year-round, or for seasonal foraging. Because suitable brackish marsh is present within the Action Area, and no

barriers to dispersal occur between onsite brackish marsh and documented occurrences in the adjacent Eden Landing Preserve, this species is assumed to occur throughout suitable brackish marsh and adjacent grassland habitat in the Action Area.

California Clapper Rail

California clapper rails have been documented to occur along Old Alameda Creek during the Invasive Spartina Program surveys (Olofson Environmental, Inc. 2020). Additionally, the project's consultant conducted 2 passive surveys in 2019 with positive detections. Vocalizing birds were estimated to be as close as approximately 100 feet from the survey stations, as well as at other locations within 656 feet (200 meters) of the physical project area and at greater distances both up- and downstream of the physical project area. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume California clapper rails are present in Action Area.

Effects of the Action

Effects of the Action are all consequences to listed species or critical habitat that are caused by the proposed action, including the consequences of other activities that are caused by the proposed action. A consequence is caused by the proposed action if it would not occur but for the proposed action and it is reasonably certain to occur. Effects of the Action may occur later in time and may include consequences occurring outside the immediate area involved in the action.

Approximately 0.073 acre of salt marsh habitat and directly adjacent vegetated areas that will be affected. Of that total, 0.031 acre will be a permanently affected and 0.042 acre will be temporarily affected but lost to the species for 3-5 years. The temporary impacts will be minimized by revegetation. The ruderal non-native grassland habitat will be allowed to revegetate naturally and is expected to have cover similar to pre-disturbance conditions within 1-2 years after completion of construction. The marsh habitat will be revegetated using plants salvaged on-site and/or with plants purchased at a local nursery. The revegetation area will be monitored annually until cover is similar to that of the adjacent undisturbed areas. It is expected to take 3-5 years for the marsh vegetation to return to pre-disturbance cover amounts, a longer-term affect to the species than a true temporary effect. Permanent wetland impacts were compensated for by purchasing credits at San Francisco Bay Wetland Mitigation Bank but this bank is wetland bank only and is not Service-approved to sell salt marsh harvest mouse or California clapper rails credits.

Implementation of the proposed project will result in less frequent maintenance than is currently required. The reduction in maintenance-related disturbance will benefit the habitat and associated species in this part of the Old Alameda Creek.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

Equipment noise, vibration, and increased human activity may interfere with normal behaviors. These behaviors include feeding, sheltering, movement between refugia and foraging grounds, and other essential behaviors. Intolerable levels of disturbance that may force individual mice to flush from cover or prevent them from seeking available cover could expose them to a predation

risk that otherwise would not occur.

Although vegetation removal will reduce the potential for mortality from entombment or crushing during construction activities, salt marsh harvest mice will still be affected. Depending on time of year and food availability, the relocation to adjacent habitat could be energetically costly due to a lack of familiarity with the microhabitat and result in lower survivability. Individual salt marsh harvest mice that move into adjacent upland habitat may be exposed to increased predation levels during more frequent active movement to forage or seeking shelter in vegetation communities with less dense canopy cover where there are predators present. Displaced salt marsh harvest mice may also be subject to increased competition for resources in a more densely occupied habitat or habitat which contains sparser patches of suitable food. Disturbance to females from September to November, during the latter part their breeding season of March to November, could result in consequences such as nest abandonment or failure of the current litter. Therefore, displaced salt marsh harvest mice will likely suffer from increased predation, competition, and potentially reduced reproductive success overall.

It is also possible some individuals could be accidentally harmed or killed during construction activities by equipment, or the transport of materials on access routes. The implementation of the *Conservation Measures* described in the *Description of the Proposed Action* section for the salt marsh harvest mouse will also ensure the likelihood of harm, injury, and mortality resulting from the proposed action remains low.

California Clapper Rail

Any California clapper rails occupying habitats within 656 feet of the construction zone would likely be subject to noise and visual disturbance. Equipment noise, vibration, and increased human activity may interfere with normal behaviors. These behaviors include feeding, sheltering, movement between refugia and foraging grounds, and other essential behaviors. Intolerable levels of disturbance may force individual CCR to flush from cover or prevent them from seeking available cover and could expose them to a predation risk that otherwise would not occur. Noise or other construction disturbance during the CCR breeding season (February 1- August 31) could result in the loss of breeding activity or nest abandonment and the loss of all eggs and chicks in the nest. To minimize these effects to breeding, work is planned to occur September 1 – January 31, which is outside of the nesting season for this species. There are surrounding areas of suitable habitat beyond 656 feet that could provide refugia and shelter during the construction.

Cumulative Effects

Cumulative Effects include the effects of future State, Tribal, local or private actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area considered in this biological opinion. Future Federal actions unrelated to the proposed project are not considered in this section, because they require separate consultation pursuant to section 7 of the Act. During this consultation, the Service did not identify any future non-Federal actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area of the proposed project.

Conclusion

After reviewing the current *Status of the Species* for salt marsh harvest mouse, the *Environmental Baseline* for the Action Area, the *Effects of the Action*, and the *Cumulative Effects*, it is the Service's biological opinion that the proposed project is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail. The Service reached this conclusion because the project-related effects to the species, when added to the environmental baseline and analyzed in consideration of all potential cumulative effects, will not rise to the level of reducing the likelihood of survival or recovery of the species based on the following: (1) construction effects like noise disturbance will be temporary and overall disturbance will be reduced as maintenance activities will not be needed as frequently; (2) significant mortality or reduction in the population size is not anticipated to result from the proposed project, and (3) the amount habitat affected by the proposed project will not be permanently altered, fragmented, or reduced in foraging and sheltering quality to the extent the population of salt marsh harvest mouse or California clapper rail in the area is at risk of extirpation.

INCIDENTAL TAKE STATEMENT

Section 9 of the Act and Federal regulation pursuant to section 4(d) of the Act prohibit the take of endangered and threatened species, respectively, without special exemption. Take is defined as to harass, harm, pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture or collect, or to attempt to engage in any such conduct. Harass is defined by Service regulations at 50 CFR § 17.3 as an intentional or negligent act or omission which creates the likelihood of injury to a listed species by annoying it to such an extent as to significantly disrupt normal behavioral patterns which include, but are not limited to, breeding, feeding or sheltering. Harm is defined by the same regulations as an act which actually kills or injures wildlife. Harm is further defined to include significant habitat modification or degradation that results in death or injury to listed species by significantly impairing essential behavioral patterns including breeding, feeding, or sheltering. Incidental take is defined as take that is incidental to, and not the purpose of, the carrying out of an otherwise lawful activity. Under the terms of section 7(b)(4) and section 7(o)(2), taking incidental to and not intended as part of the agency action is not considered to be prohibited taking under the Act, provided that such taking is in compliance with the terms and conditions of this Incidental Take Statement.

The measures described below are non-discretionary, and must be undertaken by the Corps so that they become binding conditions of any grant or permit issued to the applicants, as appropriate, for the exemption in section 7(o)(2) to apply. The Corps has a continuing duty to regulate the activity covered by this incidental take statement. If the Corps (1) fails to assume and implement the terms and conditions, or (2) fails to require the (applicants) to adhere to the terms and conditions of the incidental take statement through enforceable terms that are added to the permit or grant document, the protective coverage of section 7(o)(2) may lapse. In order to monitor the impact of incidental take, the Corps must report the progress of the action and its impact on the species to the Service as specified in the incidental take statement [50 CFR § 402.14(i)(3)]

Amount or Extent of Take

The Service anticipates incidental take of salt marsh harvest mice and California clapper rails will be difficult to detect or quantify for the following reasons: the inherently elusive behavior, the propensity to move rapidly through vegetation, and their cryptic occupancy of vegetation types resulting in low detectability. There is a risk of injury or mortality as a result of the proposed activities and subsequent temporary loss or degradation of suitable habitat. Therefore, the Service anticipates take incidental to the proposed action in the form of harm, including habitat modification, injury, or mortality, of all salt marsh harvest mice within the 0.073 acres of coastal brackish marsh habitat physically affected in the Action Area and harm, by impairing essential behaviors such as foraging or predator evasion, of all California clapper rails in the adjacent salt marsh habitat within 656 feet of the project construction areas (approximately 5 acres). Upon implementation of the following reasonable and prudent measures, incidental take of salt marsh harvest mouse associated with the project will become exempt from the prohibitions described in section 9 of the Act. No other forms of take are exempted under this opinion.

Effect of the Take

In the accompanying biological opinion, the Service determined that the level of anticipated take is not likely to jeopardize the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail.

Reasonable and Prudent Measure

All necessary and appropriate measures to avoid or minimize effects on the salt marsh harvest mouse resulting from implementation of this project have been incorporated into the project's proposed *Conservation Measures*. Therefore, the Service believes the following reasonable and prudent measure is necessary and appropriate to minimize the incidental take of the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail:

1. The Corps through the applicant and its contractors will minimize the potential incidental take of the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail.

Terms and Condition

In order to be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, the Corps shall ensure compliance with the following term and condition, which implement the reasonable and prudent measure described above. This Term and Condition is non-discretionary.

1. Term and Condition 1 implements Reasonable and Prudent Measure 1:
 - a. At least 15 days prior to the proposed project implementation, the Corps and/or the applicant will submit to the Service, for approval, the name(s) and credentials of biologists it requests to be biological monitors specified for this proposed project. Information included in a request for authorization must include, at a minimum: (1) relevant education; (2) relevant training on species identification,

survey techniques, handling individuals of different age classes, and handling of different life stages by a permitted biologist or recognized species expert authorized for such activities by the Service; (3) a summary of field experience conducting requested activities (to include project/research information and actual experience with the species); (4) a summary of biological opinions and/or informal consultations under which they were authorized to work with the listed species and at what level (such as construction monitoring versus handling), this should also include the names and qualifications of persons under which the work was supervised as well as the amount of work experience on the actual project including detail on whether the species was encountered or not; and (5) a list of 10(a)(1)(A) permits, if any, held or under which individuals are authorized to work with the species (to include permit number, authorized activities, and name of permit holder).

- b. The Corps shall minimize the potential for harm, killing or other forms of take of the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail from project-related activities by implementation of the *Conservation Measures* proposed in the *Description of the Proposed Action* in this biological opinion.
- c. The Corps shall ensure that their applicant immediately notifies the Service of any killed, injured, or entrapped salt marsh harvest mice or California clapper rail, within one (1) working day of the detection. Please contact the Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at: San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office, 650 Capitol Mall, Suite 8-300, Sacramento, California 95814 or by telephone at (916) 930-2664.
- d. The Corps and/or their applicant shall educate and inform personnel involved in the project as to the *Conservation Measures* and *Terms and Conditions* in this biological opinion.
- e. The Corps shall comply with the reporting requirements of this biological opinion, including a post-construction report outlining how the *Conservation Measures* were implemented for this project.
- f. The Corps and/or their applicant shall ensure any personnel identified as biological monitors or biologists, who are responsible for ensuring compliance with the *Conservation Measures* or other parts of the project which may affect federally-listed species, be Service-approved prior to implementing those activities.

Reporting Requirements

In order to monitor whether the amount or extent of incidental take anticipated from implementation of the project is approached or exceeded, the Corps shall adhere to the following reporting requirements. Should this anticipated amount or extent of incidental take be exceeded, the Corps must reinitiate formal consultation as per 50 CFR § 402.16.

- 1) The Service must be notified within 24 hours of the finding of any injured or dead listed species or any unanticipated damage to its habitat associated with the proposed project. Injured listed species shall be cared by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person, such as the Service-approved biologist for the proposed project. Notification will be made to the contact above in Term and Condition 1c, and must include the date, time, and precise location of the individual/incident clearly indicated on a U.S. Geological Survey 7.5 minute quadrangle or other maps at a finer scale, as requested by the Service, and any other pertinent information. When an injured or dead individual of the listed species is found, the Corps shall follow the steps outlined in the Salvage and Disposition of Individuals section below.
- 2) Sightings of any listed or sensitive animal species shall be reported to the Service and the CNDDDB (<https://www.wildlife.ca.gov/Data/CNDDDB/Submitting-Data>).
- 3) The Corps' applicant shall submit a post-construction compliance report prepared by the on-site biologist to the San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office within 60 calendar days of the date of the completion of construction activities. This report shall detail (i) dates that construction occurred; (ii) pertinent information concerning the success of the project in meeting the avoidance and minimization measures; (iii) an explanation of failure to meet such measures, if any; (iv) known project effects on the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail, if any; (v) occurrences of incidental take of this listed species, if any; (vi) documentation of employee environmental education; and (vii) other pertinent information.

Salvage and Disposition of Individuals

Injured listed species must be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person(s), such as the Service-approved biologist. Dead individuals must be sealed in a resealable plastic bag containing a paper with the date and time when the animal was found, the location where it was found, and the name of the person who found it, and the bag containing the specimen frozen in a freezer located in a secure site, until instructions are received from the Service regarding the disposition of the dead specimen. The Service contact persons are the Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at (916) 930-2664; and the Resident Agent-in-Charge of the Service's Office of Law Enforcement, 5622 Price Way, McClellan, California 95562, at (916) 569-8444.

CONSERVATION RECOMMENDATIONS

Section 7(a)(1) of the Act directs Federal agencies to utilize their authorities to further the purposes of the Act by carrying out conservation programs for the benefit of endangered and threatened species. Conservation recommendations are discretionary agency activities to minimize or avoid adverse effects of a proposed action on listed species or critical habitat, to help implement recovery plans, or to develop information. The Service recommends the following actions:

- 1) Encourage or require the use of appropriate California native species in restoration efforts.
- 2) Facilitate additional educational programs geared toward the importance and conservation of tidal marsh and seasonal wetlands.
- 3) Assist the Service with implementing other recovery actions identified within the most current recovery plans for salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail.

In order for the Service to be kept informed of actions minimizing or avoiding adverse effects or benefiting listed species or their habitats, the Service requests notification of the implementation of any conservation recommendations.

REINITIATION – CLOSING STATEMENT

This concludes formal consultation on the Union Sanitary District Emergency Outfall Project. As provided in 50 CFR § 402.16,

- 1) Reinitiation of formal consultation is required and shall be requested by the Federal agency or by the Service where discretionary Federal agency involvement or control over the action has been retained or is authorized by law and:
 - A) If the amount or extent of taking specified in the incidental take statement is exceeded;
 - B) If new information reveals effects of the action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not previously considered;
 - C) If the identified action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat that was not considered in the biological opinion;
or
 - D) If a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the identified action.
- 2) An agency shall not be required to reinitiate consultation after the approval of a land management plan prepared pursuant to 43 U.S.C. 1712 or 16 U.S.C. 1604 upon listing of a new species or designation of new critical habitat if the land management plan has been adopted by the agency as of the date of listing or designation, provided that any authorized actions that may affect the newly listed species or designated critical habitat will be addressed through a separate action-specific consultation. This exception to reinitiation of consultation shall not apply to those land management plans prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604 if:

- A) Fifteen years have passed since the date the agency adopted the land management plan prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604; and
- B) Five years have passed since the enactment of Public Law 115-141 [March 23, 2018] or the date of the listing of a species or the designation of critical habitat, whichever is later.

If you have any questions regarding this biological opinion, please contact Kim Squires, Section 7 Division Chief (Kim_Squires@fws.gov) at the letterhead address or at or at 916-930-5634. Please reference the Service File Number 08FBDT00-2018-F-0238 in any correspondence regarding this project.

Sincerely,

Kaylee Allen
Field Supervisor

LITERATURE CITED

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http://www.spartina.org/documents/ISPRIRARReport2019_001.pdf

U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service. 2013. Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California. Sacramento Fish and Wildlife Office, Sacramento, California. xviii + 605 pp.

https://www.fws.gov/sfbaydelta/EndangeredSpecies/RecoveryPlanning/Tidal_Marsh/Documents/TMRP_Volume1_RP.pdf

WRA Environmental Consultants. 2018. Biological Resources Assessment USD Emergency Outfall Project. 44 pp.